

About the project

The main objective of OH4Surveillance is to support the participating countries to set up and scale up One Health surveillance to priority pathogens in an efficient, coordinated and collaborative manner.

The scope of OH4Surveillance is limited to One Health surveillance aiming to protect public health through the early detection of emerging and re-emerging zoonotic pathogens in animals and environment. The setting up and scaling up activities includes capacity building and surveillance activities, and is done in close collaboration with EFSA and ECDC as well as with other related projects.

OH4Surveillance runs for three years (01.01.2024-31.12.2026).

#OH4Surveillance

[linkedin.com/company/oh4surveillance/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/oh4surveillance/)

[@OH4Surveillance](https://twitter.com/OH4Surveillance)

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One 4Health SURVEILLANCE

Setting up a
coordinated
surveillance under the
One Health approach

Why a One Health Approach?

One Health is a collaborative, multisectoral, and transdisciplinary approach that recognises the interconnection between people, animals, plants and their shared environment and ecosystems.

The majority of new emerging infectious diseases that affect humans are zoonoses, infections that can be transmitted between animals and humans.

There is a pressing need for more rapid and effective responses to zoonotic diseases, which can be achieved with a One Health approach.

Objectives

- Set up and scale up One Health surveillance
- Contribute to collaborative approaches across countries to prepare for cross-border health threats
- Collaborate across project partners and external stakeholders and ensure synergies with national and international networks

Targeted surveillance activities

The planned setting up and scaling up activities will develop, build on, upgrade and extend One Health surveillance based on each country's needs, while aligning with the European wide frameworks and strategies.

Working groups with specific surveillance focus composed of experts from participating countries are setup, to allow for knowledge exchange and networking across the project.

Key references:
<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7882>

<https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2023.EN-7812>

Consortium

 Statens Serum Institut (SSI)
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

 Swedish Veterinary Agency (SVA)
Folkhälsomyndigheten (FOHM)

 Luxembourg Institute of Health (LIH)
Administration luxembourgeoise vétérinaire et alimentaire (ALVA)

 Ruokavirasto
Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL)

 Folkehelseintituttet (NIPH)
Veterinærinstituttet (NVI)

 Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut (FLI)

 Nacionalinis maistro ir veterinarijos rizikos vertinimo institutas (NMVRVI)
Nacionaline visuomenės sveikatos prižiūros laboratorija (NVSPIL)

 Państwowy Instytut Weterynaryjny (PiWet)

 Sciensano

 Partikas un veterinārais dienests (FVS)
BIOR
Slimību profilakses un kontroles centrs (SPKC)

 Riigi Laboriuuringute ja Riskihindamise Keskus (LABRIS)
Eesti Maaülikool (EMU)
Põllumajandus- ja Toiduamet (PTA)
Terviseamet (TA-Health Board)

11 countries
11 beneficiaries
11 affiliated entities

